

STUDENT - THE NECESSITY AND POSSIBILITIES OF FORMING A CULTURE OF USING FREE TIME IN THE SPIRITUAL UPLIFTMENT OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation.

The article deals with the problems of organizing the culture and use of leisure time of youth.

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Society is interested in the ability of each citizen to effectively utilize their free time for their socio-economic development and spiritual growth. This is primarily due to the life of the student-youth, which is the most active and organized socio-demographic group in society. Therefore, it is necessary to address the problem of regulating their leisure time in today's conditions.

The system of regulation of student-youth leisure also includes fostering a culture of leisure. In our opinion, in this direction, first of all, it is necessary to create certain conditions to meet the existing needs, as well as to encourage the formation of new needs that meet the more stable levels of students and their culture.

Leisure culture is a qualitative description of a person's participation in socially significant activities that help him realize his creative potential using various forms and methods of leisure.

The value of time and leisure in personal and social life, work and life, the creation of a socio-psychological basis for the formation of a culture of leisure among students has always been an important task, and as society develops, the requirements for leisure culture are growing.

Therefore, the analysis of leisure culture is related, on the one hand, to the qualitative changes taking place in the leisure activities of student youth, and, on the other hand, to the formation of clear goals in their leisure activities.

The process of forming a culture of leisure of students consists of the following stages:

- The first stage is strategic, to constantly develop the desire of students to engage in socio-cultural creativity in their spare time:

- The second stage is a tactical stage, the wider involvement of students in individual and socially significant forms of leisure, taking into account the needs and interests of young people;

- The third stage is the process-technological stage, the solution of material-technical, organizational-methodological, personnel-related activities related to the organization and regulation of leisure time of students.

In the first stage, the participation of students in socio-cultural creative activities in their spare time leads to the emergence of a certain system of valuable areas. These are a set of objective factors that influence the formation of a culture of leisure for students.

In the second phase, which is directly related to various aspects of leisure activities, the study of the interests and motives of students affects their direct participation in activities of social significance.

It is known that the weakening of the role of social institutions such as the family, schools, youth unions, higher and secondary special education institutions in the implementation of socialization tasks and the emergence of new forms and types of leisure, the lack of methods to manage them "How to manage?" The question is on the agenda.

According to many researchers, the culture of leisure is primarily a person's inner culture, consisting of a set of personal qualities such as needs, interests, goals, tastes, skills, intelligence, and they allow to spend leisure time purposefully, usefully, meaningfully [4 .P. 64].

At the same time, it should be noted that the personal characteristics of each person require the organization of free time, its use, a separate consideration of the social phenomena of this phenomenon. This situation is closely related to the availability and level of functioning of cinemas, stadiums, museums, libraries, which are important components of the system of organization and use of leisure time. This is one of the important aspects related to the content of organizing and managing students' leisure time.

Today, a certain system of effective organization of spiritual and educational work in leisure time has been created in our country, and hundreds and thousands of spiritual and educational events are held in them. Higher education institutions are also covered by a whole system of spiritual and educational activities through conversations, discussions, meetings, the organization of various clubs. However, it is difficult to achieve our goal due to

the lack of harmony between our social goal of building a new Uzbekistan, which embodies the ideas of humanity, goodness and creativity, and our social responsibility to mobilize, social cooperation and social activism. This means that the spiritual and enlightenment work we organize in our free time can achieve our goal only if we can ensure a direct balance between the social purpose and social responsibility of society.

Understanding the nature of free time depends on the level of self-awareness of each person through the spiritual world. The level of self-awareness, on the other hand, is manifested in relation to different age groups of a person.

Based on the results of theoretical and experimental research on the problems of ontogeny psychology, which covers the life of a person from infancy to student life, it can be shown that the following periods are based on the generalization of many sources analyzed:

1. Childhood. In the early stages of infancy, the world, information about all objects, bodies, imaginations, emblems, etc., becomes a spiritual treasure as a product of the child's interaction with adults, leaving traces under the shell of his cerebral hemispheres. At most stages of this period, the child does not have the opportunity to acquire knowledge and experience, independent acquisition of learning, skills and abilities [2.P.88]. From the age of 3 to 6 months, when a child begins to develop a desire to interact with adults, as he approaches the age of one, in addition to consistently observing the behavior of adults, he gradually develops a desire to participate in their activities.

2. Early childhood. In the human ontogeny, during the period of growth from 1 to 3 years of age, various manifestations of mental reflection are formed, such as the most important qualities of the human race, traits, attitudes to the environment, others, behavior, thinking and consciousness.

The pre-school age group includes 3-6 year olds and will be able to manage their desires. It is relatively easy to subdue them to the whims of adults, parents, coaches.

Children at this age will have relatively calm, more stable emotions.

3. The junior school age includes primary school (1-4) students from 6 to 10 (11) years of age.

Until that time, they had acquired this or that information under the direct guidance of adults, but now they try to get the necessary information, to set a clear and definite task for themselves, with their own will, in accordance with a certain motivation.

4. Adolescence is a period of 11 (12) -15 years, during which they form worldviews, beliefs, point of view, self-awareness, evaluation and so on.

5. Early adolescence. Early adolescence covers 15-18 years (high school students, academic high school, vocational college students). They are at the stage of striving for spiritual achievement, having the opportunity to test themselves in high school where they can work independently after completing their physical education, become citizens of the country at the age of 16 and have the right to vote and be elected at the age of 18. All this is a set of conditions necessary for the early adolescents to grow socially as citizens, to decide their own destiny and to grow spiritually as a successful person. Social activism, changes in educational movements in the early adolescents lead to the formation of a scientific outlook, a stable belief, the strengthening of a creative approach to the acquisition of knowledge, the formation of independent thinking.

6. Student period. The student is a social group that prepares to perform the roles of social life and specialization in material and spiritual production on the basis of certain rules and special program, includes an average of 17-23 years old and consists of the second stage of adolescence. One of the features of socio-psychological development in this period is the growing activity of reading, along with the growth of conscious motives, independence, initiative, interest in social situations, moral rules, the desire to understand them, which are the most important qualities of behavior.

It is known that one of the main tasks of the university is to teach students to work with the main sources of educational materials, to organize its independent educational activities, to acquaint them with the methods of self-management. Ability to organize learning activities independently requires expediency, planning, regularity, consistent learning activities at all stages of education. Likewise, the ability to organize leisure time properly is associated with regularity and consistency at all stages of learning. In this case, the value of free time is conditional: a) with the period from early adolescence to independent life: b) independent life in the student period, it is clear that there is a difference in understanding it in the process of activity.

This is fully confirmed by the results of a sociological survey conducted among schoolchildren and students. In school students, "while leisure perception is 36-37 percent, it can be seen that in young people, leisure is 56-57 percent."

It is clear that both categories of young people have a certain problem in perceiving and appreciating free time. Sociological research has shown that

socially active students, who study mainly for "good" and "excellent" grades, have a deeper understanding of the value of free time than others. It can be seen that there is an intrinsic connection between the spiritual world of man and the rational organization of leisure.

In this regard, it is necessary to pay special attention to the problem of meeting the healthy spiritual needs of students and young people in their spare time.

It is well known that spiritual needs differ from material needs in a number of specific ways. Spiritual needs change not only during historical development but also in the process of individual development.

The assimilation of spiritual values is carried out by people in their spare time as a specific process of mutual spiritual exchange and spiritual communication.

It is impossible to ignore the growing ignorance based on blind adherence to spiritual knowledge, especially in today's world of shallow, destructive, and corrupt "works."

That is why President Sh.Sh. Mirziyoev paid special attention to this problem and said: "When we say ignorance, we usually mean religious ignorance, fanaticism. But the fact that today's life processes occur in all spheres of life of ignorance shows that if it is not fought against in time, it can lead to very serious consequences. Today, we face the scourge of ignorance in all spheres of our lives, both in the economy and in the system of education, health care and culture, and this evil is in our hands and feet. There can be no talk of progress and development without this shackle.

At the same time, we have a lot of important tasks ahead of us in the fight against ignorance in the field of culture, teaching our youth to understand the real art, shaping their aesthetic world on a sound basis. [1.P.].

Limiting people's spiritual needs based on certain norms is a very complex process.

The formation of a healthy spiritual need in society is therefore also important, as the spiritual and moral level of man and society becomes poorer, so does the psychology of material consumption and bigotry.

Spiritual activities in leisure time in higher education institutions are of interest to every student, both spiritually, creatively and practically.

The need for development in every human being, the sense of striving for perfection, manifests itself as will, spiritual action, inner strength, and spiritual

need. In this, the spiritual need has a special place, and its satisfaction in a rational, healthy way is of great importance for human perfection.

A healthy spiritual need is the basis of human and social development, the driving force behind its development. Satisfying a healthy spiritual need means that society strives for perfection, for everyone to strive for perfection. This, knowledge, social experience, self-education, striving for development are also important aspects of the formation of a healthy spiritual need. A healthy spiritual need not only reminds everyone of their imperfections, but also encourages them to regular perfection.

Unfortunately, in addition to the fact that the scientific literature has not yet clearly defined the concept of "healthy spiritual need", there is no system of criteria, indicators and signs that determine their level.

In our opinion, a healthy spiritual need is a specific spiritual need that serves the perfection of each person on the basis of the ability to think independently and critically evaluate their needs within a certain norm, enriching and developing positive abilities and qualities, and thus positively affects the development of society system.

In addition, the system includes the ability to define a clear situation and prospects for each person, the ability to take advantage of opportunities to act in specific situations, moral culture, the ability to use leisure time wisely.

"Unhealthy spiritual need" is a need that creates negative spiritual and moral defects in a person, leads to the endless growth and depravity of desires, and thus poses a threat to society.

Healthy spiritual needs manifest themselves in the form of the need to know, the aesthetic need, the moral need, the religious need, because they include such areas as truth, beauty, purity, faith, goodness, and the pursuit of justice. Some of these needs are formed through human perceptions, imagination, perception, emotions. Others are related to the process of thinking.

Therefore, in order to properly organize student leisure time and achieve the desired goal, it is necessary to study the socio-spiritual environment in each community, to develop the ability to observe the events around us, to create a balance of social purpose and social responsibility.

Given these circumstances, students can carry out a lot of social, cultural, educational and spiritual activities in "extracurricular time".

In our opinion, in addition to reading, the following directions can be distinguished as components of time:

1. Independent work in the field of science taught in the classroom:

2. Participation in social activities:
3. Visits to cultural and art institutions:
4. Reading fiction, use of mass media:
5. Doing sports:
6. Communication with friends, acquaintances, parents, relatives:
7. Internet, computer games:
8. Participation in various clubs:
9. Religious activities:
10. Passive rest.

If a student is engaged in one of these areas, that is, reading a book, watching a play in the theater, watching a movie in the cinema, or engaging in any sport, it is not possible to say that his time is "empty." On the contrary, his time is meaningfully organized and affects his health and spirituality.

Accordingly, the level of consciousness, culture, thinking of each person can be assessed in terms of how they organize their free time.

A person who realizes how important the lack of meaningful organization of leisure is for his personal development, the development of society, does not waste any minute of time, spends it primarily for his physical and spiritual development, and thus serves the development of his country.

Student is a necessary part of the leisure time budget for young people. Extracurricular time serves to make the time allotted for study more meaningful and complete when it is used by the student for a specific purpose, spiritual and physical development.

Therefore, in order to form a culture of leisure, it is necessary to pay special attention to:

1. Pre-set clear goals and objectives for the effective use of free time and act accordingly.
2. To understand that the effective organization of leisure time is a relative concept, a means of achieving learning activities, a healthy lifestyle, physical and spiritual maturity.
3. Achieving the transformation of meaningful and effective organization of leisure time into a daily lifestyle.
4. Focus on creating the conditions and opportunities necessary to increase the efficiency of leisure.

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